

2. Acoustic courtship signals of *N. lugens*. A. Female (macropterous or long-winged) signal. B-C. Male (macropterous or long-winged) signal. Time marks at 1-S intervals, RC: 0.007 s.

of the sclerite and the top of coxata are densely covered with rectangular chitinous scales.

As a calling adult slightly vibrates its abdomen in a dorsoventral direction, the sclerite rubs against the top of the coxata. The acoustic signal emitted is a series of clicks or discrete sound pulses (Fig. 2).

This signal-producing mechanism was verified in an experiment where adults with the two friction surfaces topically glued were unable to call.

The wave pattern, pulse repetition frequency, and sonic spectrum of the signals are closely related to the abdominal action and acoustic characteristics of the insect body. There is, however, no significant variation in those aspects between macropters and brachypters.

The acoustic signal is transmitted through the substrate of the host plant, making it possible for a small insect such as BPH to transmit a faint audio-frequency signal; transmitting efficiency is much higher than through air. The legs, and sometimes the feeding stylet, are believed to be the connection from the insect to the host plant for transmission and reception. No special hearing organ has been found, even under scanning electron microscope. Perhaps BPH responds to the signals through tactile sensations in its legs.

Several species of other common planthoppers — *Sogatella furcifera*

(Horvath), *S. longifurcifera* (Esaki et Ishihara), *Laodelphax striatellus* (Fallen), *Nilaparvata bakeri* (Muir), *N. muii* China, *Paracorhulo sirokata* (Matsumura et Ishihara), *Toya*

propinqua neopropinqua (Muir), and *Saccharosydne procerus* (Matsumura)—have similar acoustic signal-producing organs. BPH is considered to be representative of delphacids. □

Occurrence of flour mite *Acarus siro* Linn. in rice mills

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A. siro (*Tyroglyphus furinae* Linn.), a polyphagous flour mite, was reported for the first time in milled rice samples collected from storage godowns in Cuttack, Puri, and Balasore districts of Orissa 1984-86. We examined 25-g samples under stereoscopic binocular microscope to determine mite population (eggs, juveniles, and adults). Grain moisture content of each sample was measured by the Oswa Universal

Moisture Meter.

Stored rice harbored a range of mite populations, depending on storage period, rice variety, and grain moisture. Mite populations showed significant differences among four test varieties—CR1014, Ratna, Jaya, and Pusa 2-21 (see table).

The mite occurred in almost all samples collected from 10 rice mills. Mite populations increased significantly across storage from 6 to 24 mo. Grain moisture of the samples ranged from 16 to 19%, considered a congenial moisture range for mite multiplication. In addition, the mite was found in such rice products as bran and suji (powdered rice) stored in godowns of the mills. □

Population of flour mite in milled rice. Orissa, India, 1984-86.

Storage period (mo)	Mites ^a (no./25-g sample)			
	CR1014	Ratna	Jaya	Pusa 2-21
6	86 a	73 a	65 a	39 a
12	158 b	139 b	128 b	47 ab
18	183 bc	152 bc	148 c	110 c
24	284 d	228 d	253 d	149 d

^aMean of 20 samples. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.